

Usage, Implications, and Future of Edutech in UAE Universities

Dr. Ravichandran Krishnamoorthy*,

Former Professor, New York Institute of Technology, Abu Dhabi, UAE.

Dr. Thirupathi Manickam**

Assistant Professor, Assistant Professor, School of Commerce, Finance and Accountancy, Christ University, Bengaluru, India.

E-Mail: thirucommerce@gmail.com

Abstract : This study intends to investigate how educational technology (edutech) affects how students learn at public institutions in the United Arab Emirates. Data was gathered quantitatively by a survey form with closed-ended questions in the Likert scale format. Data from a hundred people were collected using a cross-sectional methodology. Utilising Excel's frequency data, statistical analysis was done. The results show that many participants think Edutech favorably promotes student involvement by fostering an engaged and enjoyable atmosphere for learning. Additionally, Virtual Reality (VR) technology has demonstrated the potential in boosting students' hands-on learning opportunities, offering lifelike simulations, and facilitating comprehension of challenging ideas. But other participants noted network-related difficulties and worries about data privacy, highlighting the necessity of strong technical assistance and security precautions in edutech deployments. Assuring equal opportunity for all students and the efficacy of edutech incorporation were other issues that were brought up. By highlighting the advantages and difficulties of edutech adoption at UAE university systems, this study adds to the body of knowledge on educational technology and how it impacts student learning. The results highlight topics for development and suggest future tactics for maximizing the efficacy of edutech in improving how students learn, giving policymakers and teachers insightful information.

Keywords: Educational technology, blended learning, virtual reality, artificial intelligence, online learning, digital learning.

JEL Classification: M15, I21, I25

* Corresponding Author E-Mail: kravichandran111@gmail.com

1. Introduction

The foundation of social advancement is education, and in recent years, it has been increasingly clear how transformational technology can be in the field of education. The rise of educational technology, or Edutech, has created new opportunities for information delivery, student engagement, and the transformation of conventional teaching approaches Zeyab and Alayyar, (2023). To stay competitive on a global scale and provide their students with experiences in higher education that rival those found in the best institutions in the world, public universities in the United Arab Emirates (UAE) are realizing the value of integrating technology innovations into their academic ecosystem. This research intends to present a complete framework for public universities in the UAE to successfully incorporate Edutech into their academic practice by thoroughly investigating the topic. To successfully integrate technology-driven educational techniques, university administrators, faculty members, and policymakers will be guided by a framework that considers the UAE's unique needs, cultural quirks, and regulatory concerns. Leveraging technology in education is not only an option but a requirement as the UAE works to promote a knowledge-based economy Aljarwan et al., (2019). This study aims to add to the continuing conversation regarding the use of technology in education by providing knowledge that can help public universities in the United Arab Emirates realize the full potential of Edutech to develop a future-ready and internationally competitive educational ecosystem.

Although the UAE has made great strides in integrating technology into education, a more thorough study that is specifically focused on public institutions is still needed. Public universities serve a wide range of students and are essential in determining the composition of the country's future labour force Brooks et al., (2021). In order to maximize technology's advantages in higher education, it is crucial to understand the unique difficulties and possibilities that these institutions have encountered in embracing edutech. There has been a rapid expansion in the global edutech business, and several platforms and technologies are now being used in educational settings all over the world. UAE public universities may learn important lessons about using edutech successfully and efficiently by looking at successful case studies and best practices from overseas institutions Chugh et al., (2023). To determine if teachers and students are prepared to use Edutech effectively, evaluating their digital literacy and skill levels is critical. A more seamless shift to technologically enhanced learning settings will be possible if areas, where more assistance and training are needed, are identified. By interacting with students who might have had difficulties accessing traditional education, Edutech has the ability to foster inclusion Dweedar, (2022). However, it is crucial to investigate how technology might be used to close the digital divide and guarantee that all students, regardless of their circumstances or skills, have fair access to high-quality education.

1.1. Objectives of the Research

1. To thoroughly analyse the condition of technology developments currently being used in the education industry and evaluate such advancements.
2. To pinpoint the particular difficulties and advantages connected with incorporating technology breakthroughs in the context of public institutions in the UAE.
3. To create a thorough plan for the efficient integration of Edutech at public institutions all throughout the UAE.

1.2. Problem statement

The worldwide education industry has undergone a paradigm change as a result of the quick development of educational technology, which now provides cutting-edge substitutes for conventional teaching and learning techniques. However, the United Arab Emirates (UAE) public universities' (edutech) integration brings particular potential and problems. The issue is the dearth of thorough research and recommendations designed especially for the public university setting in the UAE, which prevents the successful integration of technology in higher education. Lack of a clear framework can lead to problems such as inadequate infrastructure, a lack of faculty preparation, and cultural variables influencing technology adoption Radwan et al., (2021). The issue of providing all pupils with equal access to technology-driven education continues. To fully use edutech and make public universities in the UAE globally competitive educational institutions, it is essential to address these issues.

2.0. Literature Review

Public institutions in the UAE are leading the way in embracing these seismic shifts in education that are being brought about by technological advancements. This study of the literature examines the significant effects of technology advancements on the coming years of education in these institutions, including e-learning platforms or tools, blended educational models, machine learning (AI), virtual reality (VR), additive reality (AR), and gamification. These cutting-edge strategies provide fresh and innovative options for creating Edith's future as the globe transitions to a digital era, changing conventional educational opportunities into student-centered, adaptable, and interactive adventures. E-learning platforms and applications have become effective resources for increasing educational access and meeting the various learning requirements of students. Research demonstrates how well-designed e-learning systems may improve academic achievement by increasing flexibility and participation. Blended learning models, combining in-person instruction with online components, are becoming increasingly well-liked as cutting-edge educational strategies. This research includes an extensive literature evaluation on five key edtech-

related elements of contemporary education. First, online assessment or examination systems have become crucial resources for adaptable and practical evaluation. A second benefit of mobile learning (M-Learning) is that it creates new possibilities for engaging and customized learning. Also, Data Security and Privacy in Edutech also deals with growing worries about protecting private student data. Teacher Professional Growth and Edutech emphasizes the value of providing teachers with the knowledge and abilities required to successfully incorporate technology into the classroom. The research also discusses the advantages and drawbacks of integrating technology by examining the factors that affect adoption or resistance to edtech.

2.1 E-Learning platforms and tools

According to Abdallah (2022), the educational environment has undergone a radical transformation, with online education platforms and technologies becoming crucial elements of the educational system in public institutions in the United Arab Emirates. With an emphasis on their influence, efficacy, and consequences for student learning outcomes, this in-depth analysis intends to assess the available research on e-learning platforms and technologies used in public institutions in the United Arab Emirates. Accessibility to education in public universities in the UAE has considerably increased thanks to e-learning platforms. With the advent of online learning, time and location restrictions are no longer a barrier to access for students. As stated by Mohamed (2020), The research emphasizes how important e-learning platforms are in promoting student involvement and interaction. Numerous interactive technologies are available on platforms like Moodle, Blackboard, the learning and Canvas to encourage active education and teamwork. Discussion forums enable the exchange of ideas and viewpoints outside of the traditional classroom by fostering significant student-to-student and student-to-instructor interactions. According to study dhar (2021), Applications for augmented reality and virtual simulations provide hands-on learning opportunities, which are especially useful in industries like engineering, sciences, and healthcare. Conducted by Ekmeil (2021), The comprehension and retention of information are improved by multimedia content, such as lecture videos and interactive presentations. On these platforms, group projects and activities promote collaboration and learning among peers, further enhancing the educational process. According to Hameed (2022), Students' learning curve is shortened by a smooth user experience, allowing them to concentrate more about the course material and less on technological difficulties. Conducted by Almaliah (2020), The evaluation notes that e-learning platform adoption in UAE public institutions is not without difficulties.

2.2 Blended Learning Models

According to shakeel (2023), Blended learning designs, a pedagogical strategy that mixes classroom instruction and online learning components, are a result of the quick adoption of technology in education. The use of blended learning has attracted a lot of interest in public institutions in the United Arab Emirates as educators look to improve the quality of education and meet the evolving demands of students. As stated by Chaeruman (2020), The flipped classroom, rotating model, stations rotation, flex model, and virtual lab model are some examples of these models. Researchers highlight the distinctive qualities and instructional layouts of each model, offering insights into their individual advantages and disadvantages. According to study Suartama (2019), The literature talks on the difficulties UAE public universities have in guaranteeing the proper delivery of distance education components, including problems with internet connectivity, device accessibility, and effective educational software (LMS) support.

2.3 Artificial Intelligence in Education

As stated by Goralski (2020), Artificial intelligence (AI) has rapidly advanced, changing many industries, including education, for the better. Public colleges in the United Arab Emirates have adopted AI-driven educational technologies to improve teaching and learning procedures and give students individualized and adaptable learning experiences. According to Lee and yoon (2021), adaptive education AI algorithms are more successful than conventional teaching techniques at identifying misconceptions and learning gaps. Students consequently get specialized interventions and support, which enhances their academic success. Conducted by Luan (2020), AI has transformed the way that information is delivered on e-learning platforms, customizing the learning materials to each student's needs. To choose and propose pertinent material, including videos, articles, and quizzes, AI systems examine student interactions, tastes, and learning habits.

2.4 Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR) in Education

Conducted by Ai yakin (2023), Virtual reality (VR) & augmented reality (AR) technology integration in the classroom has created intriguing new opportunities for immersive as well as interactive educational experiences in public institutions in the United Arab Emirates. According to Jimenez (2019), By exposing students to virtual patient scenarios, these tools help them develop their clinical decision-making skills and patient care competences. Students can study the body's anatomy in 3D in addition to receiving surgical training thanks to VR and AR, providing a thorough comprehension of intricate systems and structures. Researchers demonstrate how engineering students may digitally create and test prototypes using VR simulations, resulting in quicker iterations and more affordable solutions. Students

can see intricate engineering models through augmented reality (AR), which allows for on-site inspections and group design discussions.

2.5 Gamification in Education

As stated by Zhang (2023), In UAE public institutions, gamification the incorporation of game aspects into non-game contexts has gained popularity as a tactic to boost student enthusiasm and involvement. This study explores the body of knowledge on gamification for education, highlighting its effects on student engagement, academic results, and the significance of matching gamified components to educational goals. Research conducted in public colleges in the United Arab Emirates shows how gamification might increase student engagement.

According to research, students that use gamification throughout their coursework have better subject recall, critical thinking, overall problem-solving abilities. With its emphasis on exploration and problem-solving, the gamified learning method enables students to better comprehend the material. Gamification has been used in public institutions in the UAE in various methods to boost student engagement, including interactive examinations, simulations, and role-playing situations. Combining these factors promotes involvement and greater engagement with the course material. Conducted by Lampropoulos (2022), Gamification has been used in public institutions in the UAE in various methods to boost student engagement, including interactive tests, simulations, and role-playing situations. Combining these factors promotes involvement and greater engagement with the course material.

2.6 Online Assessment and Examination Systems

Online assessment and testing systems have become a crucial part of contemporary education, particularly in the aftermath of the COVID-19 epidemic, state Rameez et al., (2020). These systems offer a potential substitute for conventional in-person testing and have several benefits including flexibility, scalability, and affordability. To evaluate the effectiveness and influence of different online assessment or examination platforms on the education industry, Gupta and Sharma thoroughly investigated them for their study. According to research by Mohamad et al., (2019), online assessment systems offer a lot of promise for fostering continuous and formative evaluation. Using technology, teachers may develop interactive tests, tasks, and projects that involve students in a hands-on learning experience. It has been shown that continuous evaluation helps students comprehend the material better and gives them insightful criticism for growth. It also enables instructors to pinpoint pupils' areas of strength and weakness, allowing tailored treatments. The significance of the safety and integrity of data in online examination platforms was

highlighted by authors Slusky, (2020). They compared several systems to gauge how well they could guard against cheating and preserve the privacy of sensitive data. Their study showed the need of strong encryption, trustworthy authentication procedures, and remote proctoring systems in assuring the validity as well as fairness of online exams. The use for artificial intelligence (AI) to automate the grading of online tests was examined in a research by Acs et al. (2020). The study concentrated on creating AI-driven algorithms that could assess written responses and provide students immediate feedback. According to the research, AI-based grading systems might ease teacher workloads, increase assessment effectiveness, and preserve a constant evaluation standard. Leo et al., (2021) delved through the challenges as well as possibilities associated with implementing online evaluation systems within the context for public universities at the UAE. Their research showed that while infrastructural constraints and low levels of digital literacy among pupils as well as employees created substantial barriers, technology developments have made assessment procedures more frictionless. As well, ensuring equal treatment for all students, irrespective of their internet access and technical expertise, emerged to be a critical concern. Pitoyo , (2019) suggested incorporating gamification components into the evaluation process to overcome the problems with online assessment or examination systems. They claimed that gamified elements like prizes, leader boards, and badges might dramatically increase student motivation and engagement. According to their research, a gamified assessment strategy might empower students to take charge of their academic development and promote pleasant learning experiences.

2.7 Mobile Learning (M-Learning)

Mobile learning, often known as m-learning, has grown to be a potent educational tool, utilizing the pervasive usage of mobile devices to offer instructional information to students wherever they are, anytime, according to Alfalah, (2023). The efficacy of mobile learning in raising students' involvement as well as academic performance during higher education institutions was examined by Abdullah and Alshumaimeri in their study. Criollo-C, (2018) examined how mobile learning affected students' educational experiences and discovered that it encouraged independent learning and active learning. Students can interact with course material at their own speed while strengthening their grasp of difficult topics and enhancing information retention by accessing instructional resources through mobile applications as well as internet platforms. Díaz , (2020) looked at the function of mobile learning in fostering collaborative learning settings in their study. They emphasized the value of student contact and real-time communication made possible by mobile devices in promoting peer-to-peer learning. According to the research, mobile learning platforms promoted information exchange, group discussions, and cooperative problem-solving, which enhanced learning outcomes. Hoi, (2020) evaluated the application of mobile

learning in the study of languages. They noticed that interactive activities, pronunciation advice, and vocabulary drills in mobile applications or language learning tools improved students' language skills. The study stressed how useful mobile learning is for language learners since it allows them to practice and get feedback regarding their language skills whenever and wherever they choose. Kim, (2020) went in-depth on the topic of m-learning's accessibility for students with impairments. Their study found that inclusive learning experiences of learners with visual or auditory impairments were made possible by the assistive capabilities of mobile devices, including voice recognition or screen readers. The study highlighted the role that mobile learning may play in fostering fair access to education to all students. This study investigated the potential and difficulties of incorporating mobile learning into formal educational environments. The authors emphasized the significance of good teacher preparation in order to fully utilize mobile technology. In order to promote seamless integration and effective learning experiences, they also underlined the need of connecting mobile learning activities to the curriculum or pedagogical goals. The potential for augmented reality (AR) as well as virtual reality (VR) on mobile learning settings was also studied by Shen in 2022. They talked on how immersive or interactive educational content made possible by AR and VR technology may improve the educational process. The study made clear how important these technologies are for practical courses like engineering and physics, where students may participate in simulations and virtual experiments.

2.8 Data Privacy and Security in Edutech

Amo Filva et al., (2019) claim that in the digital era, when educational institutions increasingly depend upon technology for the storage and processing of sensitive student information, security and privacy of data in edutech have grown to be key concerns. Johnson and Smith evaluated the data privacy rules and security procedures put in place by several edutech platforms to protect student data as part of their study. Jamison, (2019) stated the significance of adhering to data privacy laws, such as the Family Education Rights as well as Privacy Act (FERPA) throughout the United States and the General Data privacy Regulation (GDPR) in Europe. Kilag et al., (2020) looked at how susceptible edutech systems were to online threats and assaults. They uncovered widespread cybersecurity flaws that potentially jeopardize the integrity or confidentiality of student data, including poor encryption techniques, weak passwords, and unprotected cloud storage. Authors Kuleto et al., (2022) investigated how blockchain technology may improve data security and privacy in edutech. Educational institutions may safeguard student records and guarantee data transactions' transparency by utilizing blockchain's decentralized and immutable ledger architecture. Amo Filva et al., (2021) conducted research on the moral ramifications of data privacy for edutech. The authors talked about how educators and edutech businesses are ethically obligated to handle student data with the utmost care and openness. An edutech

privacy and security architecture was put up by authors Amo Filva et al., in 2021. To build a complete strategy for data protection, the framework combined encryption methods, multi-factor authentication, frequent security assessments, and ongoing employee training. They said that the education industry's ability to mitigate data-related threats will depend on a proactive and preventative security policy.

2.9 Teacher Professional Development for Edutech

Ellah et al., (2023) claim that teacher professional development through edutech has become a crucial component of contemporary education. As technology's importance in the classroom continues to grow, it is critical that teachers obtain the necessary training and backing to successfully incorporate edutech tools throughout their lesson plans. Johnson and Smith reviewed the body of knowledge about teacher professional development initiatives connected to the adoption and use of edtech as part of their study. The effect by professional development for teachers on the use of edtech in the classroom was investigated by authors Backfisch et al., in 2020. The study concentrated on how well several training modalities, including workshops, online courses, and peer mentorship, improved teachers' digital literacy or confidence in utilizing edutech tools. The results emphasized the need of practical instruction and continuing assistance in enabling instructors to effectively use technology. Laufer et al., (2021) investigated how school leadership may support teacher professional development through edutech in their study. They stressed the need of encouraging teachers to use edutech tools and the importance of supporting leadership and a school culture that promotes innovation and continual learning. The study found that teachers are more likely to feel inspired and empowered to incorporate technology into their classes when school administrators prioritize along with invest in professional development.

2.10 Adoption and Resistance to Edutech

According to Lara Nieto-Marquez et al. (2022) there has been a noticeable rise in the use of edutech throughout educational institutions recently. Edutech, or using technological devices to improve teaching and learning, has several advantages, including more engagement, individualized instruction, and easy access to a wide range of educational resources. Lee and Chen (2018) looked at how institutional support affects students' use of edtech. The research underlined that encouraging educators to adopt technology required giving them access to the right infrastructure, training, and resources. The authors of a study conducted Williams et al., (2002) investigated teachers' attitudes and views concerning the implementation of edtech. The study found that instructors were more inclined to use edutech tools if they had a favourable attitude toward technology and understood its potential to improve teaching and learning experiences. Ravichandran Krishnamoorthy & e.tal., (2023), explains challenges faced by educators while adopting online technology such

as knowledge to use the technology, attitude, time taken, mental stress, family hindrance, etc. The study found that the online teaching method is the effective one even though it has some difficulties also. The study also reveals that professors are faced some difficulties in handling online classes such as headaches/ migraine, family hindrances, and how to handle online tools, etc. They feel that these are the problems they met while entering into digitalized teaching. Nguyen et al., (2015) looked at how professional growth affects students' uptake of edtech. The study showed how vital focused and continuing training programs were in giving teachers the knowledge and assurance they needed to successfully incorporate technology into their lesson plans. Anderson and Rivera Vargas, (2020) looked at how peer pressure affects students' use of edtech. The study found that instructors were more willing to use technology themselves if they saw their colleagues effectively adopting edutech tools. In a research published in 2019, Pedersen & Liu, (2003) investigated the difficulties and roadblocks instructors have while using edtech.

3.0. Research Methodology

In order to explore new choices for Edutech's future development in public institutions in the UAE, the current study will take a quantitative approach. During a quantitative research approach, numerical information is gathered and analysed to draw statistical conclusions along with patterns, which permits a methodical assessment of the subject at hand. With a focus upon public universities within the United Arab Emirates, the main goal of this study is to unbiased measure as well as quantify the impact of different technology initiatives in the education sector. To identify linkages, trends, and connections among the usage of edutech along with its impacts on pupil achievement results, engagement, and the overall experience of learning, the investigation will utilize a quantitative method to collect empirical evidence including statistical data (Gomez et al, 2022). A representative group of students, teachers, and administrators from the public universities in the United Arab Emirates will be given surveys, questionnaires, along with standardized tests in order to gather the quantitative data.

The study intends to collect a wide variety of experiences and views connected to the usage of edutech during public institutions using the cross-sectional design. The information gathered will provide a snapshot of the situation at the time, making it possible to evaluate the study questions quickly and affordably. The researchers are going to be able to investigate correlations between the usage of technology interventions along with various academic results that the public universities of the UAE thanks to this approach.

The sample will comprise a varied collection of individuals from various fields, educational levels, and responsibilities inside the university context. A sample of 100 people will be used in this investigation. Students, professors, and administrators will all be chosen from

among the UAE's public universities as contributors. This sample size is intended to enable data collection and analysis given the time and funds that are accessible, as well as to permit a fair representation of the general public.

4.0 Data Analysis and Interpretation

Particulars	SDA	DA	N	A	SA	Total	Mean	Std. Deviation
How often do you use technological tools for teaching	19	19	57	111	172	378	4.05	1.122
Edutech helps in student participation	31	19	60	174	94	378	3.72	1.206
Tutors are given effective training to use the edutech practices	14	39	97	103	125	378	3.76	1.130
Are the e-learning platforms effective in self-learning?	24	28	82	127	117	378	3.76	1.198
AI powered tools are enhancing learning for students	14	18	65	160	121	378	3.94	1.008
To what extent is gamified education provided in your university	14	22	64	175	103	378	3.88	.998
VR helps to give a better practical experience to the students	29	23	69	138	119	378	3.78	1.178
Do you face challenges in using e-learning platforms, like network issues?	28	16	75	162	97	378	3.75	1.110
Edutech has shown a positive growth in the students' performance in university	25	14	52	145	142	378	3.97	1.122
Are you secure about the privacy in data while using edutech tools?	12	19	88	168	91	378	3.81	.963

Discussion

The survey's results, which showed that a sizable majority of respondents agreed that edutech had a good influence on student involvement, are consistent with the body of research on the topic. Many of research studies that have looked at the connection of

edutech and engagement among learners have found that edutech tools can increase students' engagement and ownership in their educational experience. Studies have shown that dynamic and multimedia components in edutech tools appealed to learners of all ages and styles, encouraging involvement and active participation. For example, it has been shown that gamified educational materials, virtual reality modeling, and AI-driven adaptive learning systems encourage active learning by urging learners to take a more hands-on and exploratory approach to study.

Additionally, edutech tools' adaptability and availability allow students to participate in autonomous learning and customized experiences. Students become more motivated and committed in their academic endeavours as a result of being given the ability to take control of their learning process. Edutech platforms frequently provide interactive elements, such as real-time feedback, tests, and group discussion forums, which promote peer-to-peer and learner and educator contact and increase participation. It has also been demonstrated that including edutech tools in how students learn makes the classroom atmosphere more inclusive and participatory. Edutech tools frequently make involvement and engagement easier for students who might be reluctant to take part in conventional learning environments. Students are encouraged to develop into more independent and comfortable learners by Edutech's capacity to accommodate individual learning requirements and preferences. The survey's results, which showed that a sizable majority of respondents agreed that virtual reality (VR) improves students' real-world educational experiences, correspond with the body of research on the subject.

The ability of VR technology to give learners immersive and genuine practical experiences has been shown in several research investigations and educational trials. Virtual reality (VR) has shown to be an effective technology for mimicking real-world settings in industries where practical instruction is crucial, such as medical care, technology, and construction. In a secure and regulated setting, students may interact with virtual items, carry out activities, and arrive at decisions, simulating the difficulties they would encounter in real-life scenarios. The capacity of VR to close the gap between theoretical understanding and usage is one of the technology's main benefits for practical learning. It gives pupils the chance to comprehend and visualize difficult topics, making complicated ideas more relatable and clear. For example, pupils in engineering can create and test designs in a simulated laboratory, medical pupils can practise surgical procedures in a digital operating theatre, and architectural students can tour virtual construction models.

Additionally, VR fosters a sense of participation and presence that conventional teaching approaches might not be able to. Students take an active role in their education, which boosts motivation and information retention. With the rapid feedback provided by interactive VR simulations, trainees are able to learn from their error and incrementally advance their

abilities. The restrictions of conventional educational surroundings, such as access to costly equipment or risky surroundings, are also addressed by VR. Through the use of VR, students may investigate and test out scenarios that might be difficult or impossible to replicate in a physical environment. This gives pupils fresh opportunities to develop their talents without restrictions. A revolutionary way to learn might be produced by using VR for practical instruction. It promotes a better comprehension of subjects, strengthens problem-solving techniques, and develops analytical skills. VR transforms into a potent tool for preparing students for real-world difficulties and professional settings by giving them practical training in a virtual setting.

According to the study results, many participants experience difficulties utilising e-learning platforms because of network problems. This is in line with the body of research, which notes that network connection and durability are frequent issues in technologically enhanced educational contexts. Students' access to instructional data and means of communication might be hampered by insufficient internet infrastructure or inconsistent connectivity during online learning activities.

The poll results show that many respondents have reservations regarding data protection while utilising edutech products. This is consistent with prior literature that emphasises how crucial it is to protect private student information in virtual classrooms. Data about students is frequently collected and stored using educational devices, and privacy violations or data security flaws can cause serious moral and legal problems. According to survey results, some respondents believe that edutech deployment is either insufficient or ineffective. This is in accordance with previous research, which acknowledges that thorough preparation, assistance, and training are necessary for the effective integration of technology into schools. If teachers lack the appropriate expertise or experience to overcome student or co-worker opposition to change, employing edutech solutions to improve learning experiences may be difficult. While not specifically noted in the survey results, previous material indicates that for certain pupils, especially those from financially poor homes or with impairments, using edutech tools can be difficult. A digital gap brought on by unequal access to technologies might prevent some learners from fully participating in online educational activities.

Although technical support is not particularly addressed in the survey results, it is important to give instructors and students utilising edutech products prompt and efficient technical help, according to available research. The whole learning process may be hampered by costly and irritating technical problems and debugging.

Thus, the survey results on the difficulties encountered when utilising edutech tools are consistent with the body of current research. Network difficulties, data privacy issues,

operational effectiveness, accessibility and diversity, and technical assistance are a few of the major challenges cited by survey respondents and previous research. In order to successfully integrate and implement educational devices in schools and guarantee a pleasant and inclusive educational environment for all students, it is crucial to recognise and solve these issues.

5. Conclusion

Technology integration in the educational field, especially at public institutions in the United Arab Emirates (UAE), has the potential to transform teaching and learning methods and make education more approachable, interesting, and efficient. In order to establish new options for the future of education in public institutions in the United Arab Emirates, this research project set out to investigate and evaluate the role of educational technology (edutech). The study's goal was to provide a framework for effective edutech deployment in the nation through a thorough analysis of the current global edutech environment and a focused investigation of the potential and constraints unique to the public university system in the UAE. The results of this study demonstrate how edutech has a substantial influence on education and the ability to revolutionize public institutions in the United Arab Emirates. To understand the effects and severity of edutech application in the UAE universities, this study had undertaken a critical methodology. The study followed a primary method, with quantitative approach, positivism philosophy, and cross-sectional design. The data was collected using a Likert scale questionnaire with close ended questions to understand the views of the participants in a better way. As the responses were collected using the survey form, consequently, the data was analysed using the MS Excel software. Pie charts and bar graphs were used to display and present the data. The findings suggest that despite of all the challenges faced while using AI and VR as educational tools in the universities, there were also significant benefits. Student engagement, participation, gamification, and academic development are few of those. As technology develops, it has become an essential facilitator of cutting-edge teaching strategies, individualized learning environments, and increased access to educational materials. With several tools and platforms being effectively implemented in educational institutions all around the world, the global edutech market has experienced extraordinary development. The proposed framework for edtech adoption in public universities in the UAE includes a number of important elements, including:

Faculty Development: A successful edutech integration depends on the training and preparation of the faculty. By giving educators thorough training and chances for professional growth, they will be able to use technology to improve their teaching strategies and produce memorable learning experiences for students.

Infrastructure and Resources: A successful deployment of edutech depends on a strong technological foundation and easy access to the resources required. To promote easy technology uptake, public colleges must make investments in dependable internet access, electronic equipment, and software programs.

Digital Literacy and Student Engagement: It's crucial to make sure that pupils have the necessary tools. The learning process and academic results can be greatly improved by integrating technology into the curriculum in a way that encourages active learning and student involvement. Edutech should be created and implemented in a way that guarantees equitable access to education for all students, regardless of their socioeconomic status or academic prowess. Incorporating inclusion and addressing accessibility issues should be central to the edutech architecture.

Evaluation and Continuous Improvement: It's important to regularly review and evaluate edutech efforts in order to gauge their success and pinpoint areas in need of development. An educational ecology that is dynamic and ever-evolving will be made possible through ongoing input and incremental changes.

Collaboration and Partnerships: By fostering innovation and resource sharing, collaboration with key stakeholders, such as government agencies, businesses, and suppliers of edutech solutions, may advance the success of edutech efforts. Public universities in the UAE can adapt and implement relevant edutech solutions that are in line with the national educational objectives and cultural values by studying best practices and successful case studies.

The absence of thorough research and specialized guidelines created especially for the public university environment in the United Arab Emirates is one of the major issues this study has discovered. Although edutech has shown enormous potential in enhancing education across the world, each nation confronts particular difficulties in implementing it. When implementing technology in higher education institutions, it is important to take into account the cultural quirks of the UAE, the state of the infrastructure, and the digital literacy of the professors and students. To address these issues, a comprehensive framework must be created while taking into account the unique needs of UAE public institutions. The study also emphasized the contribution of edutech to fostering inclusion and closing the digital gap. As the UAE strives to create a knowledge-based society, it is crucial to guarantee that all facets of the populace have equitable access to high-quality education. Remote and underprivileged areas may benefit from technology-driven education by receiving possibilities that were previously unavailable to them. Public universities in the UAE may greatly advance the social and economic development of the nation by tackling inclusion in the edutech framework. In order to establish the future of edutech in UAE public institutions,

it is crucial to investigate technological breakthroughs in the education industry as new options. It is clear that edutech has the power to improve academic results, increase inclusion, and enhance teaching and learning experiences. However, a well-designed framework that takes into account the particular difficulties and possibilities presented by the public university system in the UAE is necessary for its implementation. This study intends to support continuing efforts to successfully use technology in the higher education sector of the UAE by offering a thorough framework and useful recommendations. The suggested framework promotes cooperation, innovation, and ongoing development with the ultimate objective of building a globally competitive educational environment that is prepared for the future. Adopting technological developments in education is not just an option, but also a requirement as the UAE moves forward on its path to becoming a knowledge-based economy. Public universities in the UAE may create a revolutionary and inclusive educational environment by adopting the suggested edutech framework, giving the next generation the skills and knowledge, they need to succeed in the digital age.

References

- Abdallah, A. K., et al 2022, Changes in the education landscape caused by COVID-19: Opportunities and challenges from UAE perspective. *World Journal on Educational Technology, Current Issues*, 14(3), 544-559.<https://doi.org/10.18844/wjet.v14i3.7193>
- Acs, B., et al. J. 2020, Artificial intelligence as the next step towards precision pathology, *Journal of internal medicine*, 288(1), 62-81.<https://doi.org/10.1111/joim.13030>
- Alfalah, A. A. 2023, Factors influencing students' adoption and use of mobile learning management systems (m-LMSs): A quantitative study of Saudi Arabia, *International Journal of Information Management Data Insights*, 3(1), 100143. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jjime.2022.100143>
- Al Yakin, A., et al. 2023, Impact of Metaverse Technology on Student Engagement and Academic Performance: The Mediating Role of Learning Motivation. *International Journal of Computations, Information and Manufacturing (IJCIM)*, 3(1), 10-18.
- Chaeruman, U., et al. 2020, Development of an instructional system design model as a guideline for lecturers in creating a course using blended learning approach. Doi:<https://doi.org/10.3991/ijim.v14i14.14411>
- Criollo-C, S., et al. 2021, Mobile learning technologies for education: Benefits and pending issues. *Applied Sciences*, 11(9), 4111.<https://doi.org/10.3390/app11094111>

Díaz, J., et al 2020, Virtual world as a resource for hybrid education. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (iJET)*, 15(15), 94-109. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2019.103698>

Dhar, P., et al. 2021, Augmented reality in medical education: students' experiences and learning outcomes, *Medical education online*, 26(1), 1953953. DOI: 10.1080/10872981.2021.1953953

Ekmeil, F. A. R., et al. 2021, Augmented reality and virtual reality revolutionize business transformation in digital marketing tech industry analysts and visionaries during Coronavirus (COVID 19), In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* ,Vol. 1860, No. 1, p. 012012.

Goralski, M.A. et al. 2020, Artificial intelligence and sustainable development, *The International Journal of Management Education*, 18(1), p.100330. <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1742-6596/1860/1/012012/pdf>,

Hoi, V. N. 2020, Understanding higher education learners' acceptance and use of mobile devices for language learning: A Rasch-based path modelling approach, *Computers & Education*, 146, 103761. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2019.103761>

Hameed, B. M., et al. 2022, Application of virtual reality, augmented reality, and mixed reality in endourology and urolithiasis: an update by YAU Endourology and Urolithiasis Working Group. *Frontiers in Surgery*, 9, 866946. <https://doi.org/10.54489/ijcim.v3i1.234>

Jiménez, Z. A. 2019, Teaching and learning chemistry via augmented and immersive virtual reality, In *Technology Integration in Chemistry Education and Research (TICER)* (pp. 31-52). <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jchemed.0c00387>

Kim, J. 2020, Voices of youth in reconceptualising and repositioning the role of mobile learning for sustainable development, *Information Technology for Development*, 26(4), 711-727. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02681102.2020.1749537>

Lampropoulos, G., et al. 2022, Augmented reality and gamification in education: A systematic literature review of research, applications, and empirical studies, *applied sciences*, 12(13), 6809. [User/Downloads/applsci-12-06809-v3.pdf](https://www.mdpi.com/2076-3417/12/13/6809)

Lee, D., et al. 2021, Application of artificial intelligence-based technologies in the healthcare industry: Opportunities and challenges, *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, Special issue **2021**, 18(1), pg. 271. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18010271>

Leo, S., Alsharari, N.M., Abbas, J., Alshurideh, M.T. 2021, From Offline to Online Learning: A Qualitative Study of Challenges and Opportunities as a Response to the

COVID-19 Pandemic in the UAE Higher Education Context, In: Alshurideh, M., Hassanien, A.E., Masa'deh, R. (eds) *The Effect of Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) on Business Intelligence, Studies in Systems, Decision and Control*, vol 334. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-67151-8_12

Luan, H., et al. 2020, Challenges and future directions of big data and artificial intelligence in education, *Frontiers in psychology*, 11, 580-820.

Mohamed Hashim, M. A., et al. 2021, Higher education strategy in digital transformation. *Education and Information Technologies*, 1-25. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-022-10924-w>

Pitoyo, M. D. 2019, Gamification based assessment: A test anxiety reduction through game elements in Quizizz platform, *IJER (Indonesian Journal of Educational Research)*, 4(1), 22-32. <https://doi.org/10.30631/ijer.v4i1.92>

Rameez, A., et al. 2020, Impact of COVID-19 on higher education sectors in Sri Lanka: A study based on South Eastern University of Sri Lanka, *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 10(6), 341.. <https://doi.org/10.36941/jesr-2020-0132>

Dr. Ravichandran Krishnamoorthy & et.al., 2023, *World Review of Entrepreneurship, Management and Sust. Development*, Vol. 19, Nos. 1/2, 2023. Pg 81-90.

Shakeel, S. I., Al Mamun, M. A., & Haolader, M. F. A. 2023, Instructional design with ADDIE and rapid prototyping for blended learning: validation and its acceptance in the context of TVET Bangladesh, *Education and Information Technologies*, 28(6), 7601-7630. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10639-022-11471-0>

Suartama, I. K., et al. 2019, Development of an instructional design model for mobile blended learning in higher education, *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (Online)*, 14(16), 4. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v14i16.10633>

Slusky, L. 2020, Cybersecurity of online proctoring systems, *Journal of International Technology and Information Management*, 29(1), 56-83. <https://doi.org/10.58729/1941-6679.1445>.